

Additional file 1

Figure S1. Purification profile of the different cellulosomes by gel filtration chromatography. *C. thermocellum* growth media were centrifuged (10,900 g, 7 min), and the supernatant fluids were carefully removed from the pellet and concentrated 40 times using a Pellicon XL Biomax 300 Cassette (Millipore, Cat. No. PXB300C50). Concentrated samples were fractionated by size exclusion chromatography using a HiLoad 16/600 Superdex 200 prep grade gel filtration column (GE Healthcare). (A) Chromatogram of glucose-derived cellulosomes (B) Chromatogram of CB-derived cellulosomes (C) Chromatogram of MCC-derived cellulosomes (D) Chromatogram of aISG-derived cellulosomes (E) Chromatogram of aICS-derived cellulosomes (F) Chromatogram of acCS-derived cellulosomes. Fractions containing the cellulosomes (according to SDS-PAGE analysis) are marked by black arrows. All cellulosome-containing fractions eluted immediately after the void volume, due to the separation range of the column.